

Annual Report

2025

SND

Swedish National Data Service

Contents

Preface	3	International collaboration & projects...	18
SND Network	4	ATRIUM	19
Members of the SND Network	5	CESSDA ERIC	19
Network activities	6	DDI Alliance	19
Full-day meetings and conferences.....	6	EOSC	20
Webinars	7	Skills4EOSC	21
SND Consortium	8	Statistics	22
Steering Committee	9	Catalogue usage metrics.....	23
The Consortium Advisory Council	9	Top 3 downloads.....	24
Flagships	10	Top 3 requested collections	24
Chalmers, KTH, University of Gothenburg, and the SND Office	10	Number of catalogue entries 1982–2025...	25
Karolinska Institutet	10	Economy	26
Lund University	11	Statement of financial performance for 2025	27
Stockholm University	11	Staff	28
“Optimists”	11	SND office	29
National collaboration & projects	12	Domain Specialists	31
ART<3DATA project on artistic research data	13		
The KAFFE project	13		
Openscience.se	14		
Mistra Co-Creating Better Blue (C2B2).....	14		
Researchdata.se.....	15		
Training activities.....	16		
Development projects in DORIS	17		

Preface

2025 has been a strategically important year for the Swedish National Data Service (SND). In March, we launched Researchdata.se, which is being established as the national web portal for high-quality, well-documented research data across a wide range of disciplines. By providing a single point of access to research data suitable for reuse, the portal forms a central part of SND's efforts to achieve open access to publicly funded research data, in line with national and EU objectives.

The KAFFE project delivers a comprehensive overview of how effectively Sweden's current research e-infrastructure supports researchers' needs in managing research data. It was finalized at the end of 2025, and its findings will inform the ongoing reorganization of the national e-infrastructure landscape.

SND remains an active part of Sweden's engagement with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and, together with Sunet and SciLifeLab, contributes to a proposal coordinated by the Swedish Research Council to establish a Swedish EOSC node.

In June, the Swedish Research Council reported to the Government on how Sweden's national research e-infrastructure could be developed through enhanced coordination and organizational reform. The proposal recommends that the Council assume national coordination responsibility for basic digital research e-infrastructure, including data networks, research data management and reuse, secure data services, large-scale computing, and storage. Under this

model, the Council would retain responsibility for the infrastructure delivered through Sunet and assume responsibility for the research infrastructure currently provided by SND, while Linköping University would deliver services through NAISS. Further government mandates are expected in early 2026.

The SND Network continues to demonstrate strong commitment and engagement in events and working groups; it is an indispensable part of our national infrastructure. A particular highlight of the year was a joint meeting with the SND Steering Committee, the Consortium Advisory Council, and the DAU Council, focusing on shared future challenges.

The coming year will be pivotal. As the final year of our current funding period, 2026 is expected to bring clearer direction from the Government regarding the future of Sweden's e-infrastructure for research. My ambition is to help secure long-term sustainable funding for SND, contribute to the establishment of a nationally coordinated e-infrastructure organization, and lay the foundation for a Swedish EOSC node – all in close dialogue and collaboration with our

community: Swedish universities, research infrastructures, public agencies, and other relevant stakeholders.

Eva Stensköld
Director

SND Network

In 2025, SND organized a variety of webinars, workshops, and in-person events for the SND Network. The two in-person network meetings, in Gothenburg in April and in Malmö in October, were highly appreciated and had some 100 participants each. The network meetings are primarily in-person, but presentations were live-streamed for digital participants from the network. In collaboration with the Artistic Faculty at the University of Gothenburg, SND also organized a well-received symposium on research data from artistic research.

Staff from the SND main office have visited several of the member organizations of the SND Network to discuss the practical work in managing and sharing research data. The SND office has also maintained regular contact with many Data Access Units (DAUs) on issues regarding data management and access to research data.

Members of the SND Network

At the end of 2025, the SND Network consisted of the following member organizations (Consortium organizations in bold text).

1. Blekinge Institute of Technology
2. **Chalmers University of Technology**
3. Dalarna University
4. Halmstad University
5. Jönköping University
6. Karlstad University
7. **Karolinska Institutet**
8. Kristianstad University
9. **KTH Royal Institute of Technology**
10. Linköping University
11. Linnaeus University
12. Luleå University of Technology
13. **Lund University**
14. Malmö University
15. Mid Sweden University
16. Mälardalen University
17. Swedish Veterinary Agency
18. RISE Research Institutes of Sweden
19. Royal College of Music
20. Sophiahemmet University
21. Stockholm School of Economics
22. **Stockholm University**
23. Swedish Defence University
24. Swedish Geotechnical Institute
25. Swedish Polar Research Secretariat
26. **Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences**
27. Södertörn University
28. Swedish School of Sport and Health Sciences
29. **Umeå University**
30. University College Stockholm
31. University of Borås
32. **University of Gothenburg**
33. University of Gävle
34. University of Skövde
35. University West
36. **Uppsala University**
37. Örebro University

Network activities

Full-day meetings and conferences

SND network meeting in Gothenburg

 8-9 April

Main theme: The complex relationship between policy and practice in the transition to an open science system. The meeting highlighted the gap between policies, regulations, and guidelines on various levels that regulate how open science is expected to be implemented in Sweden's higher education institutions, and the actual practices of researchers.

Art, Knowledge, Context – A Symposium on Artistic Research

 2 October

A one-day symposium in collaboration with the Artistic Faculty at the University of Gothenburg, discussing documentation and knowledge transmission in artistic research.

SND network meeting in Malmö

 22-23 October

Themes: The KAFFE project – significant results and future impact, and AI in the research data process, about what role AI can play in the work with research data, and what new opportunities the technology might offer.

Meeting for SND's legal network

 19-20 November

Themes: Personal data and pseudonymization in the light of new EU legislation, and copyright and open data.

Webinars

Analysing text collections in Mink – Språkbanken’s data platform

 26 February

An introduction to Mink and how to use it to process and analyse text material.

Research Data Alliance and Sweden in a global context: Opportunities, experiences, and future engagement

 4 March

A presentation of the Research Data Alliance (RDA) and examples of RDA engagement, followed by a discussion on ways forward for RDA Sweden.

Digital Q&A about Researchdata.se – main features and contents

 31 March

Following the launch of Researchdata.se on 25 March, SND introduces the website and answers questions from the SND Network.

Data Down Under: Three Australian Infrastructures on Research Data Management and Sharing

 22 May

Three presentations from leaders within the Australian Research Data Commons and the Australian Data Archive, ADA.

Data Drop-In: Get our help in reviewing and publishing research data

 Spring

Digital sessions where SND’s Research Data Advisors offer support to DAU staff.

Q&A on new procedures for handling datasets in DORIS and SND CARE

 1 & 2 October

Information about the procedures for handling datasets shared via DORIS and SND CARE, which have been reviewed to clarify the division of responsibilities for “data in” and “data out”, and to ensure that SND’s work aligns with agreements and other relevant documentation.

Synthetic data, bias, and metadata for transparency

 7 October

An introduction to key concerns around bias in synthetic datasets, tools for bias-assessment, and how metadata can help make such biases and other generative “hallucinations” more transparent.

The transition to an open Science system – some practical examples

 16 December

Practical examples from members of the SND Network on how they are working to support the transition to an open Science system.

SND Consortium

SND is governed by a consortium consisting of nine universities: University of Gothenburg, Chalmers University of Technology, Karolinska Institutet, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Lund University, Stockholm University, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Umeå University, and Uppsala University. The University of Gothenburg is the host university of SND, and the SND main office is in Gothenburg.

Steering Committee

SND's Steering Committee consists of representatives with expertise in infrastructure and research data matters. The members of the Steering Committee are:

- **Hans Karlsson**, Professor in theoretical chemistry, Uppsala University (chair)
- **Marianne Gullberg**, Professor in psycholinguistics, Lund University
- **Sverker Holmgren**, Professor in scientific computing and Director of Chalmers e-Commons, Chalmers University of Technology
- **Vigdis Kvalheim**, Head of unit for research and knowledge resources, Sikt, Norway
- **Hanna Lindroos***, Head of Data Management Support, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
- **Cecilia Martinsson Björkdahl**, Head of Compliance & Data Office, Karolinska Institutet
- **Sebastian Meijer***, Professor of health care logistics, KTH
- **Johan Rung**, Head of SciLifeLab Data Centre, Uppsala University

SND's Steering Committee had four meetings in 2025, one of which was a residential meeting to facilitate more in-depth discussions. Their discussions have centred around SND's long-term development, strategy and funding with particular focus on the application for the funding period 2027–2028, which was submitted in March 2025, and the national investigation on how Swedish e-infrastructure for research can be developed through coordination and organizational change.

The Consortium Advisory Council

Representatives from the nine SND Consortium universities convene as a council of stakeholders, the SND Consortium Advisory Council. The council serves as a forum for information exchange and consultation among the universities in the SND Consortium. The council advises the Steering Committee on SND's strategic plan, budget, and termination plan. Additionally, it provides input to the University of Gothenburg, which administers SND's funding, regarding the Steering Committee's chair and composition, as well as the appointment of SND's Director and Deputy Director. Each university in the SND Consortium appoints one representative to the council, and the chair is from the University of Gothenburg. Björn Halleröd, Professor in sociology, University of Gothenburg, is chair of the SND Consortium Advisory Council. The council had one meeting in 2025.

*=From May 2025

Flagships

There have been four Flagship projects with activities during 2025, run by members of the SND Consortium. A Flagship is a time-limited, comprehensive project to develop routines, knowledge, and technology for research data management or data sharing. A clearly stated goal is that other higher education institutions (HEIs) shall be able to benefit from the results.

Chalmers, KTH, University of Gothenburg, and the SND Office

Traceable research data: Methods and recommendations for enhanced traceability and visibility of Swedish data publications

This flagship project aims to improve the management and traceability of data publications at Swedish HEIs. It explores how data publications can be identified, registered, and tracked over time.

By developing methods for harvesting metadata and producing practical recommendations, the project contributes to improved traceability, visibility, and quality assurance of research data, in alignment with the FAIR principles. The results will be made openly accessible in the form of current state and gap analyses, recommendations, and proposed technical solutions.

The goal of the project is to establish conditions that support national requirements for monitoring and reporting. Universities, researchers, and other stakeholders will gain support in identifying and highlighting published research data, thereby strengthening Swedish research both nationally and internationally.

Karolinska Institutet

KI Data Repository – Phase 1: Interim solution for local storage without integration with DORIS

This is a two-phase project to create a solution where researchers at KI can securely and in a structured way store sensitive data and make them accessible through SND to Researchdata.se. In the first phase (the Flagship project), this is done manually via the interim solution for local storage without integration with SND (DORIS). Phase two will involve creating a permanent local storage solution with an integration between the university storage and DORIS.

Storage is a central part of the universities' work to make research data accessible, and the results from the KI project can demonstrate how to create functional storage systems before a final integrated data storage is in place. Phase 1 was completed in 2025. The new project **KI Data Repository – Phase 2** has been approved as a Flagship project by the SND Steering Committee for 2026.

Lund University

IAC Art Files

IAC Art Files is a joint initiative by the Inter Arts Center (IAC) and the Faculty of Fine and Performing Arts at Lund University, focusing on the management of artistic research data and outputs in relation to the FAIR principles and the requirements for open research. As part of the project, a system and portal will be developed to form the basis of a new, domain-specific repository. This repository will be built, tested, and integrated at the Faculty, with the potential for national use and further development after the end of the project.

The purpose of this project is to create solutions for a domain-oriented, stable, and sustainable system for categorizing, describing, sharing, and displaying artistic research data, compatible with other systems within the university and with Researchdata.se.

Stockholm University

Certification of the Bolin Centre Database – a repository for climate, environmental, and earth system data at Stockholm University

The goal for this project is to make the Bolin Centre Database a CoreTrustSeal certified repository. The database already meets several of the certification requirements, but not all. By integrating the database with the university's central research support, functions such as IT support, data curation, legal support, and e-archives will become more accessible to the repository and contribute to its development towards a more sustainable organization. One of the long-term goals of SND's collaborations is to create

certified repositories at the HEIs in the network. The certification of Bolin Centre can serve as an example of the process, and experiences from the project can be used to facilitate future certification initiatives.

“Optimists”

In spring 2025, SND developed a new model to strengthen support for domain specialists in their work. The work is organized into so-called **Optimists** (after the small sailing dinghy) – small, time-limited initiatives that are conceptualized, developed, and followed up jointly by domain specialists and representatives from the SND Office. The Optimists are intended to benefit the SND Consortium and, ideally, the wider SND Network. They can be seen as small-scale counterparts to the Flagship initiatives contributed by Consortium members. The Optimist model is designed to enable closer collaboration among domain specialists at different Consortium universities and to highlight additional, minor contributions made by the universities.

The model was presented at the joint SND meeting in Stockholm in June. During the autumn, domain specialists began piloting the first Optimists. These pilots were successful, and the model will form the basis for most domain specialist activities in 2026. Examples of Optimists include a course module on ethical perspectives on sharing and shared research data; materials for a workshop on information security for researchers; video tutorials on how to describe 3D models of archaeological artefacts on Researchdata.se; and guidance on sharing code and population data, respectively.

National collaboration & projects

On a national level, SND collaborates with a wide range of stakeholders, such as Swedish HEIs, SUHF, the Swedish Research Council, the National Library, research infrastructures, national e-infrastructures, research funders, government agencies, and other organizations within the open science landscape in Sweden.

ART<3DATA project on artistic research data

The ART<3DATA project began in the fall of 2022 as an internal SND focus study, aimed at a better understanding of the concept of research data from artistic research. The study has received growing interest from many parties in the Swedish landscape of artistic research; the smaller artistic universities and colleges in Stockholm, as well as the artistic faculties at the larger universities. SND has become an important voice on the national arena in terms of advice on artistic research data management (ARDM). The project will result in a report containing the fundamental skills for research data advisors working with artistic research.

In 2025, the work consisted of compiling the results from the project so far and presenting them in different contexts. 1 April, SND gave a presentation at the Pufendorf Institute, Lund University, at their ASG (Advanced Study Group) Creative Data Lab. The presentation is being rewritten to become a chapter in a publication from the ASG. 2 October, SND organized a one-day symposium, "Konst, kunskap, kontext" (Art, knowledge, context), in collaboration with the Artistic Faculty at the University of Gothenburg. The symposium welcomed artistic researchers as well as research support staff from all over Sweden and featured talks about the formats of research data from different kinds of artistic research. It was well received and a sequel is planned for November 2026 at the Faculty of Fine and Performing Arts at Lund University. SND was also present on the Thematic Day on Doctoral Education in Artistic Research on 3 December, organized by the Committee for artistic research at the Swedish Research Council and the Artistic Faculty at the University of Gothenburg.

Illustration by Fredric Gunve from *Art, Knowledge, Context – A Symposium on Artistic Research*

The KAFFE project – Mapping Capabilities within the E-infrastructure System for Research

In 2025, SND continued the KAFFE¹ project with the aim of providing a comprehensive overview of how effectively Sweden's current research e-infrastructure supports researchers' needs in managing research data. The project has a national perspective and was done in collaboration with other actors within the SND Network. Its outputs (due during 2026) will present a status overview of existing research data support, both for individual researchers and for project groups, as well as of the overall coordination of current e-infrastructures. It will also highlight potential gaps where specific operational capabilities are not adequately addressed.

¹ KAFFE = Kartläggning av Förmågor inom Forskningens E-infrastruktursystem (Mapping Capabilities within the E-infrastructure System for Research)

KAFFE encompasses technical solutions, organizational structures, and the competencies required for research data management. The project has been conducted through three parallel tracks: analysis of national reports and policy documents; terminology work on central concepts and the definition of key capabilities for the research process; and interviews with researchers concerning their practices and needs. Together, these tracks provide a snapshot of the current landscape, highlighting where support functions well, where gaps exist, and where better coordination is required among local, national, and international actors.

The results of the project will be compiled in a report with accompanying in-depth analyses. In the longer term, KAFFE findings are intended to support actors responsible for coordinating the development of research data e-infrastructure. This will help ensure that future initiatives relating to local, national, and international e-infrastructure solutions are designed to provide researchers with more effective and coherent support.

Mistra Co-Creating Better Blue (C2B2)

SND continues to promote open access to marine research data through the research programme Mistra Co-Creating Better Blue (C2B2). The primary channel for stakeholder interaction is via the Living Labs, where SND assists in coordinating Living Lab West. The Living Labs act as collaborative forums where diverse marine actors meet to hear about the latest developments in science and policy, discuss challenges, and jointly develop solutions for sustainable ocean governance.

Openscience.se

In 2025, SND has contributed to building the website [Openscience.se](https://openscience.se), which was launched during Open Access Week in October. The website serves as a national portal for information and guidance on open science, with the aim of supporting and advancing the transition towards a more open, transparent and sustainable research system in Sweden.

The website focuses on presenting the areas prioritized in the national guidelines for open science, the key driving and coordinating organizations, and important policy documents and resources. By providing up-to-date, quality-assured and coordinated information, Openscience.se contributes to a coherent and effective implementation of open science principles at Swedish HEIs. The target audience comprises leadership and research support functions of Swedish HEIs, although the website is also intended for other stakeholders within the research system, such as research funders, research infrastructures, and policy actors with responsibility for or an interest in open science.

Openscience.se was initiated by the Association of Swedish Higher Education Institutions (SUHF) and is developed and maintained in collaboration with SND and the National Library of Sweden (KB). The website is also supported by the Swedish Research Council (VR), Formas, Forte, and Vinnova. The content is developed, created, and managed by an editorial board comprising representatives from SND, SUHF's working group on open science, KB, and the Stockholm University Library.

Researchdata.se

Researchdata.se is a collaborative effort to create a new national portal for finding and accessing research data and training materials on research data management. Participating infrastructures, other than SND, are the Bolin Centre for Climate Research, Huminfra, InfraVis, NBIS, SBDI/GBIF, SciLifeLab, SITES, and Swedigarch. SND develops and maintains Researchdata.se with input from partners.

Researchdata.se includes the national research data catalogue with data from a wide range of disciplines. In addition to metadata from organizations actively collaborating on Researchdata.se, the catalogue also includes resources from several other sources, where information is retrieved by harvesting machine-readable metadata.

The portal also offers training resources and guides about good data management practices throughout the research lifecycle, with a focus on making data accessible and usable in line with the FAIR principles.

The portal was launched on 25 March, 2025. During the year, the development of the portal has continued

with focus on integrating more data repositories with connection to Swedish HEIs and research performing government agencies. Additional resources and guides on research data management are being developed by both SND and our partners and will continuously be added to Researchdata.se.

SND applied to be one of the initial EOSC nodes during the first enrolment call in 2024. Researchdata.se was selected as one of the 28 candidate nodes in the first round but was not selected among the final nodes. During 2025, SND has taken part in discussions about establishing of a national Swedish EOSC node, and an application has been submitted together with the Swedish research Council, Sunet, and SciLifeLab.

The EU-funded project EOSC-CONNECT was selected for funding in the HORIZON-INFRA-2025-EOSC call and will commence during 2026. In the project, the metadata catalogue of Researchdata.se will be connected to similar catalogues across Europe.

Researchdata.se is SND's largest deliverable during the current funding period.

Training activities

Training in research data management within the SND Network has continued to develop in 2025, with SND maintaining a broad and varied portfolio of training activities. These include webinars, workshops, seminars, and contributions to national and international initiatives. The demand for guidance on data sharing and reuse in the research community remains strong.

A significant proportion of effort during the year was devoted to web content for Researchdata.se, including the research data management pages and the [“Share Data: Quick Guide”](#). This work represents a sustainable, reusable training resource that can be used to support researchers throughout the research data lifecycle.

Collaboration with external experts continues to be an important element of SND’s training activities. In cooperation with Professor Ericka Johnson, Linköping University, and Dr. Jools Kasmire, Research Fellow at University of Manchester, SND produced the guide [“Managing and publishing synthetic research data”](#), which is published on Zenodo and complements SND’s broader guidance on responsible data sharing. This collaboration also resulted in the webinar [“Synthetic data, bias, and metadata for transparency”](#), held in October 2025 and now available on [SND’s YouTube channel](#), extending the reach of the training beyond the live event.

SND has also continued with the successful formula of coordinating training workshops in conjunction with the SND Network meetings. These workshops provide a forum for sharing expertise across the

network, and SND greatly values the contributions made by partner organizations. In the 2025 Network meetings, partners contributed to workshops covering open science (Chalmers), certification of repositories (Stockholm University), administrative research information (Chalmers), text analysis tools (Språkbanken Text), and archiving issues (Stockholm University and Malmö University).

In addition, SND has contributed to a range of training activities arranged by partner organizations. Of particular note in 2025 is the successful course Open Science in the Swedish Context, organized by SciLifeLab, NBIS and SND, which was an opportunity for early career researchers and data support personnel to learn about open science in practice and to build their contact network.

Development projects in DORIS

Simplified registration

In 2025, SND has introduced simplified registration in DORIS, which provides researchers with a quicker and simpler option for describing and sharing research data. It is based on a new metadata profile with fewer elements and requires a less extensive review process, offering a smoother workflow than the subject-specific metadata profiles.

Simplified registration is intended for researchers who want to make data available without providing a complete description from the outset, but who still have the option of adding further metadata at a later stage. Datasets registered in this way do not initially achieve the same degree of FAIRness, but can be gradually upgraded without undergoing a new review.

Profile for veterinary science

SND has collaborated with the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences and the Swedish Veterinary Agency to develop and implement a new metadata profile for veterinary science in DORIS. The profile includes fields for medical metadata, population, species and taxon, as well as links to biobanks or scientific collections.

There are now a total of eleven selectable metadata profiles in DORIS.

International collaboration & projects

SND is part of a global network of research data infrastructures, where collaboration has a central role. SND's international collaborations fall into two main categories: initiatives from the European Union, such as EOSC and CEESDA ERIC, and organizations that provide essential services or expertise related to research data management and repositories.

ATRIUM

ATRIUM (Advancing Frontier Research in the Arts and Humanities) is a four-year research project, funded by the European Commission, that started in January 2024. The project involves the research infrastructures DARIAH (arts and humanities), ARIADNE (archaeology), CLARIN (languages), and OPERAS (open scholarly communication in social sciences and humanities), as well as 26 additional organizations from 12 European countries. The objective of ATRIUM is to make the participants' resources better known and utilized by researchers. Other goals of ATRIUM are simplified access to the research infrastructures, improved metadata quality in catalogues and repositories, investments in materials for education and training, and increased use of controlled vocabularies and ontologies for better interoperability between systems.

SND participates in several work packages, developing reusable workflows, demonstrators, and the ARIADNE RI data portal. SND is a full member of the alliance and holds memberships in the alliance's Executive Board, Controlled Vocabularies Working Group, DDI Developers Group and Technical Committee.

CESSDA ERIC

The Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA) is an ERIC, a European Research Infrastructure Consortium, which provides large-scale, integrated, and sustainable data services to the social sciences. It brings together social science data

archives across Europe with the aim of promoting the results of social science research and supporting national and international research and cooperation.

Sweden is a member, and as a CESSDA service provider, SND is currently involved in the work on certification of repositories, training resources and events, building a common technology, and providing support and advice to prospective and new members. SND is one of the service owners of [CESSDA Resource Directory](#), which collects and disseminates resources for data archives, and provides the Swedish translations for CESSDA Vocabulary Service and the ELSST Thesaurus. In 2025, SND was instrumental in producing the [CESSDA Data Citation Guide](#), a comprehensive guide with best practices and recommendations for the entire research ecosystem.

DDI Alliance

The Data Documentation Initiative Alliance (DDI Alliance) is an international collaboration of member organizations that develops open metadata standards to enhance the quality, interoperability, and reusability of research data across the social, economic, and health sciences. The Alliance's suite of metadata standards is used as base standards for the various systems developed by SND.

SND is a full member of the DDI Alliance and holds memberships in the Alliance's Executive Board, Controlled Vocabularies Working Group, and DDI Developers Group and Technical Committee.

EOSC

The vision for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is to establish a federated European system that enables researchers to find, access, share, process, analyse, and reuse high-quality research data and services across disciplines and national borders. By promoting FAIR principles and interoperability, EOSC aims to strengthen Europe's capacity for open science and research collaboration.

During 2025, EOSC has moved further into its operational development phase through the establishment of the EOSC Federation – a federation of nodes building on existing national and European research infrastructures and services supported by the European Commission, member states, and research communities. This transition marks a shift towards a more structured and stakeholder-driven governance model, with shared responsibilities at European, national, and institutional levels.

The EOSC Association, which currently brings together approximately 250 members and observers, remains the legal entity governing EOSC. SND, with the University of Gothenburg as host university, is a member of the Association, alongside 11 other Swedish organizations, including the universities in the SND Consortium.

As EOSC enters a more mature and operational phase, discussions concerning its long-term governance and funding beyond 2027 have intensified. The development of a sustainable post-2027 model is now a central European priority, and these discussions are expected to influence the future organization of national research infrastructures across Europe.

At a national level, there is a growing interest in EOSC. We can assume that the technical and strategic development of EOSC will have significant implications for the Swedish research system. Ensuring preparedness and a shared national understanding of Sweden's ambitions and role within EOSC is therefore a common responsibility among Swedish stakeholders.

The Swedish Research Council organizes an annual national EOSC event to facilitate strategic dialogue between university leadership, government agencies, research funders, and representatives from the Government Offices of Sweden. SND contributes to this dialogue, as well as to the national coordination group for the Swedish members of the EOSC Association.

In 2025, SND has continued to play an active role in Sweden's engagement with EOSC and, together with Sunet and SciLifeLab, contributes resources to a joint proposal coordinated by the Swedish Research Council for the establishment of a Swedish EOSC node. This work aims to position Sweden as an active and well-prepared participant in the evolving EOSC Federation.

Skills4EOSC

Skills4EOSC was a three-year project funded by Horizon Europe, launched in September 2022, with 2025 representing the last half year of the project. The project brought together expertise from national, regional, institutional, and thematic open science and data competence centres from 18 European countries. Following the final project conference in June 2025 and the submission of the final report, the project received a very positive overall assessment from the reviewers, focusing on highlights such as:

- Strong recognition of the Minimum Viable Skillsets (MVS) and the related training ecosystem.
- Excellent evaluation of the Quality Assurance Framework, Recognition Framework, and the issuance of nearly 1,000 digital credentials.
- Very positive assessment of the Competence Centres Network, which is considered the key asset for long-term sustainability.
- Strong positioning of Skills4EOSC within the EOSC ecosystem and European policy landscape.

In 2025, SND continued to lead [work package 8](#), “Synergies, stakeholder engagement, advocacy, and communications”, and took part in several other work packages and tasks. Other Swedish participants and affiliated entities were Chalmers University of Technology and Umeå University, the latter playing a key role in the creation of the Nordic Data Stewardship Network (NDSN) as a demonstrable project outcome.

One of the key outputs of the Skills4EOSC was the design and creation of the Competence Centres Network (CCNet). The first General Assembly of the CCNet took place in July with two representatives from SND. The idea remains that these (currently 11) centres will carry on implementing the Skills4EOSC project outputs after the project has ended, as a platform for closer intra-European cooperation and information exchange and the mutual promotion of open science.

The logo for Skills4EOSC. The word "Skills" is written in a large, black, sans-serif font. The letter "i" in "Skills" is replaced by a vertical bar with three colored dots (blue, orange, green) above it. Below "Skills" is the text "4 eosC" in a smaller, black, sans-serif font.

Statistics

The research data catalogue on Researchdata.se includes 2,888 entries² published via DORIS.³ 181 entries⁴ were added in 2025.

² Number of datasets with at least one published, not withdrawn, version. The decrease compared to 2024 (2,938 entries) is due to the merging/withdrawal of a number of datasets after a review of the structure of data/metadata in the catalogue. Several of the withdrawn datasets are included in new "merged" versions of other datasets.

³ As of 2025-12-31. Includes entries with at least one published, not withdrawn, version. Harvested entries are not included in this statistic.

⁴ Number of entries published as a first version during 2025.

Catalogue usage metrics

Users

SND has 4,690 registered users.

There were 720 new registered users in 2025.

Catalogue page views

There were 130,114 views (or 112,379 unique views) of catalogue entries during 2025.

Downloaded material

There were in total 210,354 direct downloads⁵ from the catalogue in 2025.

Data requests

Many datasets that are not available for direct download can be requested via the Researchdata.se catalogue. In 2025, 595 requests were submitted, resulting in the dissemination of 1,184 datasets.

Data access level	Downloads
Access to data through SND – Data are freely accessible	127,659 (data and documentation)
Access to data through SND – Access to data is restricted/Data are accessible by request	67,237 (documentation only)
Access to data through an external actor	15,458 (documentation only)
TOTAL	210,354

⁵ Total number of downloads. Some downloads are comprised of several files. Attempts have been made to identify and remove automatic downloads by, for example, bots. It is, however, unlikely that they have been eliminated completely from the statistics.

Top 3 downloads

1

SCANIA Component X Dataset: A Real-World Multivariate Time Series Dataset for Predictive Maintenance

**10,896
downloads**

2

Air pollution and noise GeoTIFF files for SCAPIS environment

**6,786
downloads**

3

ACROBAT - a multi-stain breast cancer histological whole-slide-image data set from routine diagnostics for computational pathology

**5,169
downloads**

Top 3 requested collections

1

The National SOM Survey

**800 dataset
requests**

2

Swedish Election Studies - Parliamentary Elections

**247 dataset
requests**

3

Swedish Electoral Data

**76 dataset
requests**

Number of catalogue entries 1982–2025 (cumulative)

Number of catalogue entries published via DORIS (first version only) per year, cumulative. Includes a number of datasets that may later have been withdrawn, which explains the difference compared to the actual number of datasets published via DORIS in the Researchdata.se catalogue at the end of 2025.

Economy

Statement of financial performance for 2025

REVENUE	Results 2025	Budget 2025
Government grants	8,075	8 074
Sales	1,777	1 775
Internal funding	62	
Co-funding	7,024	
External research funding	20,016	20,994
Salary cost compensation from the SND Consortium	8,919	12,000
Financial gains	6	
Accruals	-695	
Depreciation coverage of grant-funded facilities	1	
Total revenue	46,575	42,843
EXPENSES		
Salary costs	-22,997	-22,664
Salary costs for the SND Consortium	-8,919	-12,000
Holiday pay costs	-67	
Other staff costs	-431	-465
Travel, representation, and PR expenses	-631	-905
Purchase of goods	-300	-495
Purchase of services	-3,628	-3,086
Indirect costs	-3,454	-3,453
Co-funding	-6,936	
Premises	-1,515	-1,769
Financial costs	-4	
Depreciation	-33	-6
Total expenses	-48,915	-44,843
Deficit/surplus for 2025	-2,340	-2,000

Figures stated in thousand SEK.

Staff

SND office

Senior Advisor
Iris Alfredsson

Research Data Advisor
Per Bergström

Research Data Advisor
Eira Brandby

Research Data Advisor
Joel Carlsten Rosberg

System Developer
Alireza Davoudian

Training Coordinator
Madeleine Dutoit

Senior Advisor
Stefan Ekman

Head of IT
Johan Fihn Marberg

Research Data Advisor
William Illsley

Research Data Advisor
Elin Hallman

System Developer
Emma Hansson

Communications Officer
Stefán Hilmarsson

Administrator and Language Coordinator
Lisa Isaksson

Deputy Head of IT and System Developer
Stefan Jakobsson

Research Data Advisor
Ulf Jakobsson

**Research Data
Advisor**
André Jernung

System Developer
Hasse Lans

System Developer
Joakim Larsson

**Research Data
Advisor**
Rufus Latham

System Developer
Tobias Linde

Senior Advisor
Gustav Nilsson

IT Technician
Alicia Olsbänning

IT Architect
Olof Olsson

System Developer
Lars Pettersson

**Research Data
Advisor**
Dimitar Popovski

**Training
Coordinator**
David Rayner

**Communications
Officer**
Helena Rohdén

Legal Officer
Erica Schweder

Director
Eva Stensköld

Deputy Director
Elisabeth
Strandhagen

Section Manager
Research Data Services
Sara Svensson

**Research Data
Advisor**
Arin Tham Savran

Senior Advisor
Karin Westin
Tikkanen

Legal Officer
Anna Wiklund
Söpke

Anna Axmon
Lund University

Nicolo Dell'Unto
Lund University

Lars Eklund
Uppsala
University

**Karin
Engström**
Lund University

Ulf Jansson
Stockholm
University

Marcus Lundberg
Uppsala
University

Karina Nilsson
Umeå University

Emilie Stroh
Lund University

Ida Taberman
Swedish
University of
Agricultural
Sciences

Ylva Toljander
Swedish
University of
Agricultural
Sciences

Domain Specialists

Swedish National Data Service

www.snd.se | +46 (0)31-786 10 00 | snd@snd.se